

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN LITERATURE LESSONS

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Annotation.

This article is devoted to the issue of methods and procedures for the use of innovative technologies and interactive methods in literature lessons, the formation of the ability to effectively use the types of interactive methods.

Keywords

method, innovative technologies, literature, interactive methods, pedagogical technologies, non-traditional lessons, modern requirements.

ADABIYOT DARSLARIDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola adabiyot darslarida innnovatsion texnologiya va interfaol metodlardan foydalanish usullari va tartiblari, interfaol metod turlaridan unumli foydalanish ko'nikmasini shakllantirishga doir masalani yoritishga bag'ishlanadi. Adabiyot darslarini o`qitishda o`quvchilarda tanqidiy fikrlash ko`nikmalarini rivojlantirishninig uslibiy asoslari taqdim qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar

innovatsion texnologiya, interfaol metod, adabiyot, metod, pedagogik texnologiyalar, modernizatsiya, tanqidiy fikrlash, kompetentlik, noan'anaviy dars.

Аннотация

Данная статья посвящена вопросу методов и процедур использования инновационных технологий и интерактивных методов на уроках литературы, формированию навыков эффективного использования интерактивных методов.

Ключевые слова

Инновационная технология, интерактивный метод, литература, метод, педагогические технологии, требование времени, нетрадиционный урок.

The President of our Republic, Sh. Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, emphasized the importance of the role of education in the nation's action towards a specific goal: z remains an issue that will never lose its relevance and importance... In the implementation of these tasks, we rely on our national traditions formed over the centuries, the rich heritage of our ancestors", they emphasized.

It was reported that the draft decree of President Sh.Mirziyoyev was developed in order to further improve the country's education system and accelerate the development of the field of science.

The draft decree includes goals that will solve the current problems in education, show the results in the next five years, and determine the level of further development. The use of innovative technologies, modern methods and games helps to increase the efficiency of knowledge in the more interesting and in-depth study of literature in educational institutions.

It depends on the skill of the teacher to pass each lesson on the basis of a unique method, to increase the interest of students in science, to awaken in their hearts a love for science and literature. one of the tools is modern pedagogical technologies. The main goal of today's teacher is to educate well-rounded young people, to give them thorough education, to teach them to think independently, to create knowledge and life skills. and it can be done in training sessions based on innovative technologies.

Innovatsion ta'limning asosiy maqsadlari quyidagilardan iborat:

- Development of creative, communicative, intellectual potential and abilities of every student;
- Forming students as mature individuals by developing their individual qualities;
- Effective organization of the learning process;
- Development of didactic and educational activities of students;
- To be able to express personal opinion regarding learned knowledge and expressed opinions;
- Formation of critical and analytical thinking skills in students.

The main goal of innovative technologies is to bring innovations and changes to the activity of the teacher and student in the educational process, which requires the use of interactive methods. turns the lesson into an interesting activity.

For centuries, the teacher has been active in the educational process, and the student has been only a listener. In today's rapidly developing information

technology, lessons in this way do not give satisfactory results. effective organization requires increasing students' interest and ensuring their active participation in the lesson process.

In non-traditional classes, interactive methods are a tool that connects the teacher and the student. In this, a conflict of ideas occurs between the teacher and the student or between the student and the student. the use of methods increases students' free and creative thinking, develops their speech. In the course of non-traditional classes, the teacher has the opportunity to work individually with low-assimilation students, their worldview and thinking, words enriches the wealth of Z.

In this case, each interactive method should be chosen taking into account the subject of the lesson, the age of the students, their worldview, and their interests. This requires skill from the teacher. difficult to understand, the distraction of students' attention, and the decrease of their interest in the lesson. In order to avoid these situations, the teacher should always work on himself, improve his knowledge and professional skills, he should be aware of the news and achievements and be able to deliver them to the students correctly. Such tasks before the teachers require the teacher to be not only a teacher, but also an actor, director and artist.

"Cluster", "Brainstorming", "Reverse test", "Boomerang", "Fish skeleton", "Analysis of concepts", "Charkhpalak", "FSMU", "Time consumption", "Choice is optional, performance is mandatory" in literature classes the use of such methods ensures the effectiveness of the lesson and helps to increase the knowledge of students. In addition, in the case of using the relationship of literature with other subjects, such as "Yes ... no", "Find the owner of the definition", "Domino" didactic games can be used. In the process of the game, the pupils behave freely, demonstrate their knowledge, engage in discussion, and strive to prove their ideas. As a result, the pupil gains confidence and determination.

"Time consumption" method. It is effective to use this method in the form of a competition between groups in reinforcement classes after the completion of large topics or sections in literature classes. In this, students are divided into groups and turn to questions on clock-shaped visual aids located on the blackboard. For example, the teacher prepares questions on the topic "Farhod and Shirin" from the 9th grade literature textbook. Students from each group should come out and answer the hidden questions in turn. The clock indicator of the group that answered correctly moves forward. The game continues in this way. The first group whose clock indicator reaches 12 wins and is encouraged.

Through the "time consumption" method, it is possible to achieve the formation of the following skills in students:

- 1) Expressing one's thoughts and knowledge clearly and fluently orally and in writing;
- 2) Ensuring continuous strengthening of the topics covered;
- 3) Effective use of time, being able to understand one's place in class and society;
- 4) Having qualities such as reading, learning, increasing knowledge independently, being able to control oneself, etc.

Case-study technology. The use of the case method in the study of literature is based on the fact that students acquire the ability to work cooperatively, analyze, express their point of view and apply logical universal educational actions. It is also appropriate to use this method, because it allows you to form practical skills in solving problems in real life, teaches you to study, to independently search for the necessary knowledge to solve these problems. develops speech, increases self-confidence, teaches to defend one's opinion.[4;105] We will consider this based on the following examples.

Assignment on Behbudi's drama "Padarkush" based on "Case-study" technology:

Type of problem	Cause of origin	The solution
1. Ignorance of parents and children	Indifference of the father to the fate of the child	Father and child should be knowledgeable and educated
2. The transformation of the son into the murderer of the father	The fact that the child was given to immorality, that he could not choose a friend	Father should follow the advice of intellectual and teacher in time

<p>3. Politics focused on ignorance</p>	<p>That society has become a colonial nation</p>	<p>Enlightenment struggle for freedom</p>
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On the basis of case technology, students study and analyze the most important aspects of the drama. They find solutions to the problems.

Critical thinking method. This method is extremely important for today's youth. Because time is developing so quickly that it is impossible to learn all the new information. we need to sort out reliable and important information. At the same time, it is necessary not only to absorb information, but also to have the ability to understand it, analyze its essence, make a critical assessment and apply it in practice. when faced with information that is new to them, to think deeply about it in all aspects, to express a critical opinion about information and facts, to develop new ideas and evaluate them, how much of the information that has been studied and analyzed They should also be able to draw conclusions about the nature and importance of it. Using an essay for the formation of critical thinking skills is effective. the scope is not limited, it is possible to freely interpret and criticize any literary, aesthetic, philosophical, social, moral knowledge, problems. In this, the author can freely express his thoughts independently. Taking into account the age characteristics of the students, the scope of expressing opinions is narrower at first it is appropriate to teach them to write essays on various topics. If children are taught from a young age based on the development of critical thinking, they will develop their own independent opinion in various fields and topics. As a result, they will be able to approach any issue critically, read z grows up as a person who can express his opinion independently and freely, who can provide evidence for his opinion, and most importantly, who can put his ideas into practice.

The use of the above-mentioned interactive methods in literature classes helps to increase students' interest in science, to express their opinions freely and creatively, to draw conclusions by listening to the opinions of others or to argue about controversial opinions, and to defend their own point of view. creates the ground for development.

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